

Impact of Classroom Management on Students' Behavior and Learning: An Empirical Study of Secondary School Teachers in Taluka Faiz Gunj, District Khairpur, Pakistan

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to determine if there was a correlation between classroom management strategies and student engagement and achievement. Taluka Faiz Gunj's secondary institutions were the focus of the research. Teachers need effective classroom management strategies if they want their classrooms to be safe and orderly learning environments for their students. It is crucial to ensure that students have easy access to the resources they need to do their schoolwork. This study focused on secondary school educators as its participants. Random sampling was used to select 130 people to participate. A questionnaire was used for the survey. Schools were visited in person to collect data. SPSS was utilized for analysis of the collected data. Data analysis output is displayed. Demographic breakdowns of the sample are presented and analyzed. The correlation analysis revealed a connection between the two variables. The Pearson correlation coefficient between effective classroom management and low secondary school dropout rates is .810. Strong correlation between independent and dependent variables. This showed that a more organized and productive classroom environment can have a positive impact on student behavior and achievement. As a result, we have accomplished our study's aims. The research suggested that teachers should use counselling and guiding techniques to help kids with behavioral problems. For violent behavior, corporal punishment of students is inappropriate. Counseling procedures should investigate the causes of aggressive conduct and address them.

Keywords: Classroom management; Student's behavior; Student's learning

1. Introduction

The word "classroom" refers to the place in a school or college where teachers and students work together to learn. A classroom, which is sometimes called a schoolroom, is a place set aside for learning. Classrooms can be found in preschools, high schools, colleges, and even businesses and charities that offer training and education. As much as possible, the classroom is meant to be a place where students can study without being distracted (Elliot & Dweck, 2005).

Successful elementary school teachers use ways to run their classrooms to help their students do better in school. The way the classroom and school are run has a big effect on how well students learn. Effective classroom management makes students more productive in the classroom by creating an environment where they can learn about management and administration (Emmer & Stough, 2003). Assistive technologies like amplification and captioning, as well as extra staff like notetakers and interpreters, may be used as part of classroom management services. All of these things are meant to improve how engaged and successful students are in the classroom.

How to run a classroom is similar to how teachers and lecturers run their classes. In practice, this means that teachers are actually using these strategies and rules in their classes. Techniques for running a classroom are good for students and help them overcome problems that get in the way of learning and school success (Gerry & Hawking, 2002). The opposite is also true: when students and teachers are in a classroom together and the teachers use some teaching strategies to teach in a slightly different way than usual, the students benefit a lot. This means that students' ways of learning can be affected by how the lessons are taught or by how motivated and in charge the teachers are (Desai, 2006).

Academic behaviour is the full form of the word "Motive," which means to try to make someone happy by any means, including but not limited to teaching, telling stories, and being determined. The results of this study show that teachers use the success stories of many scholars, educated people, and scientists to encourage their students to study, and students see this as a change for the better in how they act in the classroom (Luis, 2002).

What teachers do in the classroom has a big impact on how their students think. Intrinsic motivation can turn students who aren't interested in learning into ambitious achievers who are obsessed with their own honor. Intrinsic behavior is any action that is done for its own sake, not to get something from the outside (Webern, 2004).

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And since classroom management suggestions often include ways to deal with bad student behaviour, teachers can understandably feel a lot of stress from their students (Lederberg, 2002). This could hurt the students' sense of what's important in life and their mental health. The stress that teachers feel because of what management does is another thing that makes kids think that life isn't worth much.

The disorder may change the student's peak periods of cognitive development, which may change how the parents feel and what they do. But it's still unclear how stress from caring for children affects family behaviour and how important the relationship between a mother and father is (Charles & Senter, 2008).

1.1. Significance of the Study

The results of this study could help teachers, students, and researchers learn more about how to teach effectively at this level. The proposed study would be good for the lives and educations of both children and their teachers and school administrators in the long run.

They can learn how to manage better to make the lives of children better in many ways. Elementary school teachers would change how they act in the classroom if they wanted to have a bigger positive effect on their students' lives.

1.2. Objective

- To study the impact of classroom management on student's behavior at Secondary Schools level in Taluka Faiz Gunj.
- To study the impact of classroom management on student's learning at Secondary Schools level in Taluka Faiz Gunj.

1.3. Research Questions

- What is the impact of classroom management on student's behavior at Secondary Schools level?
- What is the impact of classroom management on student's learning at Secondary Schools level?
- How the classroom management can be used to improve student's behavior and learning at school?

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1. Classroom Management

As part of an organization's management, planning, organizing, moving, and supervising can all be done in stages and in a continuous way to get a good performance. Klaten State Senior High School is an interesting place to do research because it is one of the official organizations that runs modern management. Klaten State Senior High School is among the institutions that have come to their senses when it comes to effective administration, planning, organization, and use of information technology in all kinds of school-related activities. With technology getting better and better at delivering all kinds of information quickly, it's important to know how important network speed is when using IT (Butar, & Kanto, 2020). To make sure that the use of IT makes teachers as effective as possible, two things must be taken into account: How important it is to have a framework that is reliable and lasts a long time; Qualified workers. The use of IT in education, which has been backed by good leadership, can speed up things like increased student engagement, creativity, innovation, and competitiveness (Darsono, & Kamal, 2018). No matter how leaders of modern businesses, like the Principal of Klaten State Senior High School, respond to the fast growth of information technology, this is an unavoidable part of running a business in the 21st century. This was clear from how the school was run and how much the head cared about using technology to help teachers do their jobs better. Leaders need to be motivated and skilled enough to move IT forward in line with the policy they've set. This is one of the most efficient and effective ways to run a modern business. This paper focuses on three main ideas: leadership, management information systems, and how well teachers do their jobs. Direction is the ability to get other people to do what you want them to do. This can work both ways. The key to being a good leader is being able to steer an organization toward its goals. This study looks at the effects of a school management program on student achievement in Sao Paulo, Brazil, using a fuzzy regression discontinuity method. The research found that some management strategies, like keeping track of performance, setting goals, and using incentives, have a big effect on 8th graders' math scores, especially for kids who don't do well in math. In terms of language, I couldn't find the same results. I dug deeper to find out if these results were caused by changes in how schools teach and run, or if they were caused by how students and teachers were chosen and how much money was spent on infrastructure. From what I've learned, I think the second option is more likely (Elacqua & Marotta, 2019). As part of an organization's management, planning, organizing, moving, and supervising can all be done in stages and in a continuous way to get a good performance. Klaten State Senior High School is an interesting place to do research because it is one of the official organizations that runs modern management. Klaten State Senior High School is among the institutions that have come to their senses when it comes to effective administration, planning, organization, and use of information technology in all kinds of school-related activities. With the development of more efficient ways to share information, users need to be aware that the speed at which they can connect to the internet is becoming more and more important to how well they can use IT. To get the most out of IT's ability to make teachers more effective, two things must be taken into account: We want a reliable

infrastructure that will last, as well as people who can do their jobs well. The use of IT in education, which has been backed by good leadership, can speed up things like increased student engagement, creativity, innovation, and competitiveness (Elacqua & Marotta, 2019). No matter how leaders of modern businesses, like the Principal of Klaten State Senior High School, respond to the fast growth of information technology, this is an unavoidable part of running a business in the 21st century. This was clear from how the school was run and how much the head cared about using technology to help teachers do their jobs better. Leaders need to be motivated and skilled enough to move IT forward in line with the policy they've set. This is one of the most efficient and effective ways to run a modern business. This paper focuses on three main ideas: leadership, management information systems, and how well teachers do their jobs. People can be made to work together toward the same goal if they can persuade and encourage each other to do so (Jain, & Mohta, 2019). The key to being a good leader is being able to steer an organization toward its goals. Most people think that the best way to measure administrative effectiveness is to look at how well leaders are able to do their jobs and reach their goals. To help teachers do their jobs better, a skilled leader may create an ideal work environment that fits their needs and motivates them to work hard and effectively (Elacqua & Marotta, 2019). This study uses the results of a recent randomized control trial in Madagascar that looked at different ways to handle management. It looks at whether or not the changes have different effects on different types of teachers. This is an important issue to look into because Madagascar, like many other developing countries, has recently hired a lot of contract or temporary teachers, who may have less training but have to work harder to get their contracts renewed. The changes in management had no effect on how well the students did in school. All different kinds of educators have the same lack of effect. It's possible that the programme is useless, at least in the context of Madagascar's education system, and it's also possible that two years is not enough time for the programme to have had a measurable effect (Jain & Mohta, 2019).

A school's success depends on how well the head of school does his or her job. Leadership is used in a school setting to help shape how students act. School leaders all over the world are starting to notice how school management trainings (SMTs) are being used to help students learn more (SLOs). Several plans are in place to support this idea, especially those that aim to improve the way schools are run. Studies in the past have shown that school leaders can come from many different places (Glewwe&Maga, 2011). Because of this, there is a need for specialized training for people who want to be in charge of running schools. In secondary school administration, a school's ability to reach its goals or objectives depends on the skills of the Head of School, who is often called the Principal, and his style of leadership. Education policy makers around the world are now paying more attention to school leadership. It is important because it affects the school's atmosphere and culture, both of which are important to the success of students. Inspiring teachers and helping them improve their skills are part of a school leader's job. Strong school leadership is important to make sure that education is effective and well-done.

2.2. Students' Behavior

This study (Tavares, 2015) looks at how well teachers do their jobs at Klaten State Senior High School to see what effect leadership and an IMIS have on teacher productivity. Using an IMIS to provide services and help teachers do their jobs better is a great example of how IT can be used in the classroom. This study has three goals: (1) to learn more about how leadership at Klaten State Senior High School affects teacher performance; (2) to learn more about how the implementation of an integrated management information system affects teacher performance at Klaten State Senior High School; and (3) to learn more about how management information from both leadership and the system affects teacher performance at Klaten State Senior High School. The sample size is 95 people, and interviews, document reviews, and questionnaires were used to get information. Using the Parson Product Moment correlation to analyze data for a required practice test (r). Chi-square analysis with a 5% significance level and multiple regression were used to see if there were any strange patterns in the data. There were positive and significant effects of leadership on teacher performance, as well as positive and significant effects of the integrated management information system on the performance of teachers at Klaten State Senior High School and positive and significant effects of the combination of these two factors on school performance. It's important to think about how command and integrated management information systems might affect how well Klaten State Senior High School teachers do their jobs (Darsono, & Kamal, 2018). As part of an organization's management, planning, organizing, moving, and supervising can all be done in stages and in a continuous way to get a good performance. Klaten State Senior High School is an interesting place to do research because it is one of the official organizations that runs modern management. Klaten State Senior High School is among the institutions that have come to their senses when it comes to effective administration, planning, organization, and use of information technology in all kinds of school-related activities. With the development of more efficient ways to share information, users need to be aware that the speed at which they can connect to the internet is becoming more and more important to how well they can use IT. To get the most out of IT's ability to make teachers more effective, two things must be taken into account: We want a reliable infrastructure that will last, as well as people who can do their jobs well. Use of information technology in education, along with

strong leadership, has been shown to improve teacher performance and speed up the process of becoming more active, creative, inventive, and competitive. No matter how a company is run, the development of information technology is an unavoidable part of modern business management. This was clear from how the school was run and how much the head cared about using technology to help teachers do their jobs better. Leaders need to be motivated and skilled enough to move IT forward in line with the policy they've set. This is one of the most efficient and effective ways to run a modern business. This paper focuses on three main ideas: leadership, management information systems, and how well teachers do their jobs. Direction is the ability to get other people to do what you want them to do. This can work both ways. The key to being a good leader is being able to steer an organization toward its goals. When do professors stop doing their best work? In semi-structured interviews, forty Israeli elementary school principals each talked about one employee who wasn't doing a good job. Half of the troublesome teachers were experienced professionals who had gone through a major personal or professional change in the middle of their careers. There's no doubt that their problems started when they were young. Many others couldn't help because they had to deal with a personal issue right away. No principal or teacher background factors were found to be linked to student achievement that was lower than average. It didn't matter where a teacher was in their career either. In this talk, we talk about the theoretical background and possible solutions (Elacqua & Marotta, 2019). Ogolla (2003) says that it's important to talk about the benefits of new and effective ways because educators' views on education change when they experience or see positive changes brought about by these techniques. Conclusions The SAIP Writing III Assessment from 2002 and a part of a theoretical model that talks about the amount of cooperation were used in this study to find out what makes teachers work together when they plan and prepare. Our results show that school factors and factors about each teacher were important predictors of how teachers worked together when planning and preparing courses. This roundtable was about what principals have to do as instructional leaders. Principals can encourage their teachers to be part of a more open professional community by making it easier for teachers to work together. The way they act here can have a positive effect on how their teachers think and feel about the world. Also, school leaders should think carefully about the issue of teachers being too busy. Lastly, going forward, we need to make sure that teachers who want to work together more are given time during regular school hours and plenty of chances to talk, both of which will help them work together more. As you can see below, there are some problems with this research. We couldn't answer some important questions about teachers' perspectives and experiences of working together because we only had secondary data. For example, we couldn't find out what makes teachers want to work together. But in the SAIP Writing III data from 2002, group lesson preparation is the type of collaboration that is talked about. Also, from these numbers, we couldn't tell what kind of organization was involved (small group, from a particular department or the school as a whole). How common other types of collaboration were at the school, whether or not participation was voluntary, and whether or not those who took part taught the same subjects or grade levels as those who took part. Whether group projects can be done in class. Whether or not the team reviewed its own performance and what the goals of the partnership were. In 2002, SAIP gave teachers a survey that wasn't meant to be used this way. So, it might be a good idea to learn more about a number of things:

- The ways principals lead in the classroom, especially when they use transformational leadership, which has been shown to have a big effect on teachers' willingness to work together.
- Factors that encourage and keep schools' collaborative teaching methods going.
- Indirect ways of working together, such as co-teaching, mentoring, etc., and the factors that predict their success.
- Cooperation between institutions (like between principals, schools, and their governing boards).

It has been shown that high school teachers have a harder time working together. Because of this, it is important to have a policy that makes teachers more aware of how important it is to work together and the good things that can come from it.

2.3. Students' Learning

The idea behind this study is that when teachers do well, students learn more and schools do better. The relational survey model was used as a method for the survey. There were a total of 426 educators who took part in the study. There were 286 women and 140 men. The above data was put together with the help of the School Effectiveness Scale (Hoy, 2014) and the Teacher Performance Evaluation Scale (zgenel, 2019). The data were looked at with the t-test, one-way analysis of variance, correlation, and regression. The results of this study show that there aren't any big differences in how teachers rate their schools based on gender or years of experience, but there are differences based on how much teachers know and how long they've been teaching. The professors who teach undergraduates had a better opinion of how well the school works than the professors who teach graduate students. In elementary and middle school, teachers' views of their schools are more accurate than in high school. Even though there isn't much of a link between a teacher's level of education and experience and how well their students do, there is a link between a teacher's gender and the grade level they teach. Women teachers usually do better in the classroom. Elementary and middle

school teachers are better at their jobs than their high school counterparts. Overall, the quality of teaching gets worse from elementary school to middle school to high school. It was found that teacher performance is moderately and positively related to school effectiveness ($r=.358$; $p.01$), and that teacher performance accounts for 12% of the total variation in school effectiveness. To put it another way, students benefit when teachers do their jobs well. Researchers found that the quality of teaching strongly predicted and affected how well students did in school. Teachers are held to a higher standard when it's clear that making good schools isn't easy and that they need to work together to overcome problems and reach basic goals. So, policymakers and school administrators might suggest that teachers evaluate their own performance, use constructive criticism, and make changes based on what they find.

3. Research Design

3.1. Type of Research

The study was a quantitative examination of the issue. Because a numerical system was used to handle the data and statistical tests were used to measure the variables. The analysis of data and the relationship between the variables were displayed graphically.

3.2. Research Method

The most important information for this study came from a survey given to secondary school teachers in the Taluka of Faiz Gunj. Both paper and electronic versions of the survey were sent out and received. All of the people who took part in the study were told what the goals were, and their privacy was kept safe.

3.3. Population

Participants for this study were the Secondary School Teachers in Taluka Faiz Gunj.

3.4. Sampling Technique and Size

Convenience Sampling was used. It is easy to approach participants at their convenience. This technique is adopted so that the school duties of participant teachers may not be affected.

And the sample size was 130.

3.5. Instruments

A questionnaire was used to figure it out. The answers were given on a 5-point Likert scale. It's a better way to get feedback from a lot of people at once. It gives back results that can be measured and analyzed in depth.

4. Data Analysis

Table 1: Demographic Data

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Male	65	50
Female	65	50
Total	130	100.0

The table shows that male 65 (50%) were private and 65(50 %) were respondents as participants of the conducted study.

Table 2: Frequency of Institutes

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Public	65	50
Private	65	50
Total	130	100

The table shows that public 65 (50%) and private 65(50 %) were respondents as participants of the conducted study.

Table: 3 Frequency of Classes

Components	Mean	Std. Deviation
Physical management	20.17	3.340
Behavior management	19.44	3.366
Instructional management	20.86	3.588
Teacher-Student interaction	19.88	3.669
Develop caring and supportive relationship	11.63	2.455

Teachers' classroom management practice of respondents (N=130)

The scores for physical management (M = 20.17, S.D = 3.340), behaviour management (M = 19.44, S.D = 3.366), instructional management (M = 20.86, S.D = 3.588), teacher-student interaction (M = 19.88, S.D = 3.669), and building caring and supportive relationships (M = 11.63, S.D = 2.455) are shown in the table below. Most teachers agree that "instructional management" is the best way to keep the classroom running smoothly.

Table 4: Academic Motivation of Respondents (N=130)

Components	Mean	Std. Deviation
Intrinsic Motivation to know	17.43	2.984
Intrinsic motivation to accomplish	17.15	3.085
Intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation	16.04	2.874
Interjected & external regulation	13.50	3.746
Extrinsic Motivation	21.61	3.234

Table 4 shows that mean value and standard deviation for the intrinsic motivation to know (M = 17.43, S.D = 2.984), intrinsic motivation to accomplish (M = 17.15, S.D = 3.085), intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation (M = 16.04, S.D = 2.874) and interjected external regulation (M = 13.50, S.D = 3.746), motivation (M = 21.61, S.D = 3.234). It is concluded that students mostly motivate extrinsically at the elementary school level.

Table 5: Relationship between Physical Management and Intrinsic Motivation to Know

		Physical Management	Intrinsic Motivation to Know
Physical Management	Pearson Correlation	1	.332
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	130	130
Intrinsic Motivation to Know	Pearson Correlation	.332	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	130	130

The relationship between physical management and intrinsic motivation to know was investigated using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. Preliminary analyses were performed to ensure violation of the assumptions of normality, linearity and homoscedasticity. There was a positive relationship between physical management and intrinsic motivation to know.

Table 6: Relationship between Physical Management and Intrinsic Motivation to Accomplish

		Physical Management	Intrinsic Motivation to Accomplish
Physical Management	Pearson Correlation	1	.223
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	130	130
Intrinsic Motivation to Accomplish	Pearson Correlation	.223	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	130	130

The relationship between physical management and intrinsic motivation to accomplish was investigated using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. Preliminary analyses were performed to ensure violation of the assumptions of normality, linearity and homoscedasticity. There was a positive relationship between physical management and intrinsic motivation to accomplish.

Table 7: Relationship between Physical Management and Intrinsic Motivation to Experience Stimulation

		Physical Management	Intrinsic Motivation to Experience Stimulation
Physical Management	Pearson Correlation	1	.260
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	130	130
Intrinsic Motivation to Experience Stimulation	Pearson Correlation	.260	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	130	130

The relationship between physical management and intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation was investigated using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. Preliminary analyses were performed to ensure violation of the assumptions of normality, linearity and homoscedasticity. There was a positive relationship between physical management and intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation.

Table 8: Relationship between Physical Management and Interjected and External Regulation

		Physical Management	Interjected & External Regulation
Physical Management	Pearson Correlation	1	.094
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.106
	N	130	130
Interjected & External Regulation	Pearson Correlation	.094	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.106	
	N	130	130

The relationship between physical management and interjected & external regulation was investigated using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. Preliminary analyses were performed to ensure violation of the assumptions of normality, linearity and homoscedasticity. There was a positive relationship between physical management and interjected & external regulation.

Table 9: Relationship between Physical Management and Motivation

		Physical Management	Motivation
Physical Management	Pearson Correlation	1	.303
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	130	130
Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.303	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	130	130

The relationship between physical management and motivation was investigated using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. Preliminary analyses were performed to ensure a violation of the assumptions of normality, linearity and homoscedasticity. There was a positive relationship between physical management and motivation.

5. Conclusions

The focus of this study is on how classroom management strategies affect students' behaviour and how well they do in school. Students staying on task and being interested in school were two main goals, and research has shown a link between good classroom management practices and these and other positive results (Merrell, 2008). The goal of this study was to find out if there is a link between using two different types of evidence-based classroom management and seeing improvements in how students behave and how well they do in school. This research has a few real-world applications that can be used in the classroom. The first thing that comes to mind is how easy it would be to put into practice. These strategies could be used as "Tier 1" classroom management in any school without any extra supplies.

The second thing that could happen as a result of this change is that more progress could be made on math fluency tasks. In particular, the results suggest that students' math skills can improve twice as fast with little extra work.

6. Recommendation

If this study or one like it were to be done again in the future, it would be good to use kids from different grade levels, schools, and parts of the country. And the intervention needs to be led by teachers who know what they are doing. You could use sound cues in the ear or color-coded cards to give consistent signals for praising and correcting desired behaviours. The dependent variable could also be changed to something else. Students in the current study were used to the two-a-day tasks, so adding a new task could help get better results. Different rates of growth are possible, especially if math probes with low variation are used and problems with ones and zeros are avoided. Lastly, each student's level of writing fluency should be taken into account by coming up with a different way to answer.

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